

Taxonomical Study of the Plants and Their Medicinal Uses in Indagaw Village, Bago Township

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Abstract

In this paper presents medicinal useful species with details of family, scientific name and its medicinal utility. Information on other general importance of medicinal is also described. 15 medicinal plants in 14 families which widely growth in Indagaw village, Bago Township. Each herb is clearly indentified by its latin name and family in addition to its common name. Identifiable descriptions are provided from diagnostic point of view. Herbs, herbal materials, herbal preparations and finished herbal products, that contain as active ingredients parts of the plant is used to treat a multitude of ailments through the village. Bioefficiency of the herbs are provided and the major therapeutic category to which the herb belongs has been mentioned.

Introduction

Medicinal plants include various types of plants. Herb refers to any part of the plant like fruit, seed, stem, bark, flower, leaf, roots, as well as non-woody plants, including those that come from trees and shrubs. These medicinal plants are also used as food, flavonoid, medicine or perfume and also in certain spiritual activities.

Plants have been used for medicinal purposes long before prehistoric period. Traditional systems of medicine continue to be widely practised on many accounts. Population rise, inadequate supply of drugs, prohibitive cost of treatments, side effects of several synthetic drugs for infections diseases have led to increased emphasis on the use of plant materials as a source of medicines for a wide variety of human ailments.

WHO estimated that 80 percent of people worldwide rely on herbal medicines for some aspect of their primary health care needs. According to WHO, around 21,000 plant species have potential for being used as medicinal plants. More than 30% of the the entire plant species, at one time or other were used for medicinal purposes. In developed countries, plant drugs constitute as much as 25% of the total drugs. Thus, the economic importance of medicinal plants is much more to countries to rest of the world. These countries provide two third of the plants used in modern system of medicine and the health care system of rural population depend on indigenous systems of medicine.

These herbal products today are the symbol of safety in contrast to the synthetic drugs, that are regarded as unsafe to human being and environment. However, the blind dependence on synthetics is over and people are returning to the naturals with hope of safety and security. It's time to promote them globally.

Scientific Name : *Justicia adhatoda* L.
Myanmar Name : Muyar-gyi
Common Name : Malabar Nut, Adhatoda
Family : Acanthaceae

Identification characters:

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A perennial shrubs, the younger stems terete. Leaves opposite and decussate, simple, the laminae elliptic, the bases acute, the margins entire, the tips acuminate, petiolate, both surfaces glabrous, exstipulate. Inflorescences axillary densely flowered. Flowered bracteate, pedicellate, bracteolate, bisexual, zygomorphic, pentamerous, hypogynous; sepals (5), fused, tooth, campanulate, imbricate, sepaloid; petals (5), fused, bilabiate, the upper half laterally inflated, the upper lips 2-fid, the lower lips 3-fid, spreading, creamish-white; stamens 2, polyandrous, petalostemonous, the anthers ditheous, sagittate, the lobe divergent at the base, inserted, introrse, longitudinal dehiscence; carpels (2), bicarpellary, syncarpous, bilocular, axile placentation, 2 ovules in each locule, the style filiform, the stigma bi-fid, ovary superior, annular disc present. Fruits loculicidal capsule, oblongoid, flattened; seeds 2, subglobose, glabrous, non-endospermic.

Uses in references-(Root) Cough; Mucolytic; Asthma; Epiphora; Stomatitis; Antidote for scorpion strings. **(Leaf)** Biliary infection; Haematemesis; Asthma; Leucorrhoea; Bleeding gums; Indigestion; Skin diseases; Hemorrhoids; Inflammation.

Scientific Name : *Rhinacanthus nasutus* (L.) Kurz

Myanmar Name : Htaw-la-butt

Common Name : Snake jasmine

Family : Acanthaceae

Identification characters :

An undershrubs, subterete, glabrous. Leaves opposite and decussate, simple, the laminae elliptic-lanceolate, the bases acute, the margins entire, the tips acute, both surfaces glabrous, petiolate, exstipulate. Inflorescences terminal paniculate cymes. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, bracteolate, bisexual, complete, irregular, zygomorphic, pentamerous, hypogynous; sepals (5), fused, the lobe linear-lanceolate, subequal; petals 2+3, fused, the tube narrow, cylindrical, the limb 2-lipped, the upper lip shortly 2-lobed, the lower broad 3-lobed, oblong, recurved, petaloid (white), glabrous; stamens 2, free, petalostemonous, on the throat of the corolla, the filament short, the anthers ditheous, basifixed, inserted, introrse, longitudinal dehiscence; carpels (2), bicarpellary, syncarpous, bilocular, 2 ovules in each locule, the style filiform, the stigma minutely bi-fid, ovary superior. Fruits loculicidal capsule, ovoid, glabrous.

Uses in references-(Leaf juice) Heal ringworm, pimples and freckles on the face.

(Root bark) Aphrodisiac; Ringworm; Herpes; Skin disease; Oedema; for dyeing hairs; As hair shampoo; Promotes growth of eyebrows. To treat numerous diseases such as Eczema; Pulmonary; Tuberculosis; Hepatitis; Diabetes; Hypertension; Snake bites.

- Scientific Name** : *Annona squamosa* L.
Myanmar Name : Aw-zar
Common Name : Custard apple, Sugar apple
Family : Annonaceae
Identification characters :

A small tree. Leaves alternate, simple, the laminae obovate, the bases obtuse, the margins entire, the tips acute, petiolate, exstipulate. Inflorescences solitary cymes. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, ebracteolate, bisexual, regular, actinomorphic, trimerous, hypogynous; sepals 3, free, ligulate, sepeloid, greenish-yellow, deciduous; petals 6, free 2-seriate, sepeloid, greenish yellow, ligulate, puberulent; stamens numerous, polyandrous, the filaments thick and short, spirally arranged, the anthers dithecal, inserted, extrorse, terminated by an enlarged ovoid connective; carpels numerous, apocarpous, monocarpellary, unilocular, parietal placentation, one ovule in each locule, the style very short, the stigma simple, ovary superior. Fruits an aggregate of berries, globose, fleshy; seeds large, brownish black, endospermic.

Uses in references- **(Root)** Oliguria; Abortions. **(Leaf)** Abscess in sores; Hysteria; Fainting spells; Ulcer; Wound; Dysentery; Ailment. **(Young fruit)** Antiseptic for sores. **(Ripe fruit)** Abscess in sores; Antipyretic for high fevers; Hair tonic. **(Bark)** Diarrhea; Diabetes. **(Seed)** Leading to blindness.

Scientific Name : *Acorus calamus* L.

Myanmar Name : Lin-ne

Common Name : Rat root, Sweet flag.

Family : Araceae

Identification characters :

A perennial herb, root stock with profusely rhizomes, strongly aromatic. Leaves distichous, simple, the laminae linear-lanceolate, the bases equitant, the margins entire, the tips mucronate, parallel veined, sessile, exstipulate, very aromatic when crushed. Inflorescences axillary spadixes, very densely flowered. Flowers ebracteate, sessile, ebracteolate, bisexual, actinomorphic, trimerous, hypogynous; perianth 6, 2 whorls in each, free, tepal orbicular-concave, brown, scarious, persistent; stamens 6, 2 whorls in 3 each, free, the filaments linear, flattened, the anthers ditheous, dorsifixed, inserted, extrorse, longitudinal dehiscence; carpel 1, monocarpellary, unilocular, axile placentation, 2 ovules in each locule, the stigma triangular. Fruits berry, turbinate; seeds few, oblongoid, endospermic.

Uses in references- (Rhizome) Cathartic; Diuretic; Antiseptic; Colic; Indigestion; Oedema; Epilepsy; Haemorrhoids; Anthelmintic; Arthritis; loss of memory; Head-ache. **(Oil)** Sedative; Hypotensive; Muscle relaxant.

Scientific Name : *Tamarindus indica* L.

Myanmar Name : Ma-gyi

Common Name : Tamarind.

Family : Caesalpiniaceae

Identification characters :

A large tree, branches spreading, glabrous. Leaves alternate, unipinnately compound, paripinnate, leaflets the laminae oblong, the bases slightly oblique, the margins entire, the tips retuse, petiolate, stipulate, caduceous. Inflorescences terminal and axillary racemes, few flowered. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, ebracteolate, bisexual, complete, irregular, zygomorphic, pentamerous, hypogynous; sepals (5), fused, the tube turbinate, the lobe oblong; petals 3+2, free, petaloid (yellowish-pink stripes); stamens 3+7st, the anthers ditheous, versatile, longitudinal dehiscence; carpel 1, monocarpellary, unilocular, parietal placentation, many ovules in each locule, 2 alternating rows on a single placenta, the style long and curved, the stigma capitate, gynophores present. Fruits pod, indehiscent, ligulate, 3-12 seeds; seeds oblongoid, smooth, non endospermic.

Uses in references- **(Root)** Amoebic dysentery. **(Bark)** Heals boils and carbuncles; As an antidote for poisons; Haemorrhoids; Polyuria; Emesis; Colic. **(Leaf)** Otagia; Prickly heats: As an antidote for snake-bite, Deodorant; Eye disease. **(Flower)** Biliusness. **(Ripe Fruit)** Internal haemorrhoid; Loss of appetite; Leprosy; Indigestion; Cholera; Heartburn. **(Seed)** Oligospermia; Polyuria; as an antidote for scorpion stings; Dysentery.

Scientific Name : *Croton tiglium* L.

Myanmar Name : Kana-kho

Common Name : Purging croton

Family : Euphorbiaceae

Identification characters :

Small trees, the younger stems stellate puberulent. Leaves alternate, simple, the laminae ovate-elliptic, the bases obtuse, the margins serrate, the tips acute to acuminate, tri-costate, petiolate, stipulate. Inflorescences terminal racemes, monoecious. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, ebracteolate, unisexual, actinomorphic, pentamerous, hypogynous. Male flower; sepals (5), synsepalous, 5-lobed, persistent; petals 5, free, linear, petaloid (white); stamens 15, disc glands 5, small, the anthers dithecous, adnate, inserted, introrse, longitudinal dehiscence; pistillode absent. Female flower; sepals (5), synsepalous, 5-lobed, stellate puberulent, persistent; petals absent; stamens absent; carpels (3), tricarpeal, syncarpous, trilocular, axile placentation, one ovule in each locule, the styles 3, the stigma 2-fid, ovary superior, stellately hispid. Fruits schizocarp capsule, elliptic-oblongoid, 3-lobed; seeds oblongoid, endospermic, fleshy.

Uses in references- **(Seed)** Ascites; Febrifuge; Leprosy; As an Antidote For scorpion stings; Purgative; Chronic; Intestinal sluggishness. **(Seed oil)** Strong laxative and irritant action. **(Root)** Jaundice; The gall bladder and liver; Hemorrhoids. **(External bark)** Jaundice.

Scientific Name : *Clitoria ternatea* L.
Myanmar Name : Aung-me-nyo
Common Name : Butterfly pea, Asian pigeonwings.
Family : Fabaceae

Identification characters :

Annual herbs, stem woody, pubescent. Leaves alternate, unipinnately imparipinnate compound leaf, the leaflets abovate, the bases acute, the margins entire, the tips retuse, the upper surfaces glabrous, the lower one pubescent, petiolate, stipulate. Inflorescences solitary and axillary cymes. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, bracteolate, bisexual, irregular, zygomorphic, pentamerous, hypogynous; sepals 5, free, campanulate, valvate, sepaloid, persistent; petals 1+2+2, free, papilionaceous, standard elliptic, purplish-blue, the wings lanceolate, yellow, the keel united at the posterior upper half, yellow; stamens 1+(9), diadelphous, staminal tube present, the anthers dithecous, dorsifixed, inserted, introrse, longitudinal dehiscence; carpel 1, monocarpellary, unilocular, marginal placentation, many ovules, in each locule, the style long and filiform, the stigma plumose, ovary superior, elongated. Fruits pod, flat, elliptic-oblong; seeds brown, endospermic.

Uses in references- (The whorl plant) Antivenin; Memory enhancing; Nootropic. **(Root and Seed)** Catharsis; Purgative; Cathartic. **(Flowers)** Amytal; Insomnia; Antistress; Anxiolytic; Antidepressant; Anticonvulsant; Tranquilizing; Sedative properties.

Scientific Name : *Mesua ferrea* L.
Myanmar Name : Gangaw
Common Name : Indian rose chestnut.
Family : Calophyllaceae

Identification characters :

Trees, the younger stems obscurely quadrangular. Leaves opposite and distichous, simple, the laminae linear-lanceolate, the bases obtuse, the margins entire, the tips acuminate, petiolate, exstipulate. Inflorescences terminal 2-5 flowered cymes. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, ebracteolate, bisexual, complete, regular, actinomorphic, tetramerous, hypogynous; sepals 4, orbicular, thick, the margins membranous, persistent; petals 4, obovate, the margins crisped, undulate, petaloid (white); stamens numerous, polyandrous, monadelphous at the base, the filament filiform, the anthers dithecous, basifixed, longitudinal dehiscence; carpels (2), bicarpellary, syncarpous, bilocular, 2 ovules in each locule, basal placentation, the style long,

the stigma peltate, ovary superior. Fruit berry, ovoid, with persistent calyx; seeds 1-4, angular, brown, non-endospermic.

Uses in references- (**Anther**) Angian pectoris; Metrorrhagia; Cystitis; Leprosy; Hypertension; Neuropathy; Carminative; Expectorant. (**Seed oil**) Aches; Chronic sores; Arthritis.

Scientific Name : *Leucas cephalotes* (Roth.) Spreng.

Myanmar Name : Pinku-hteik-peik

Common Name : Weed.

Family : Lamiaceae

Identification characters :

Annual herbs, branches diffuse. Leaves opposite and decussate, simple, the laminae ovate-lanceolate, the bases obtuse, the margins serrate, the tips acute, petiolate, exstipulate. Inflorescences axillary, verticillasters, many flowered. Flowers ebracteate, sessile, ebracteolate, bisexual, irregular, zygomorphic, tetramerous, hypogynous; sepals (10), lobed, synsepalous, the tube tubular, the lobe mouths oblique; petals bilabiate, sympetalous, the lower lip 3-lobed, spreading, petaloid, white; stamens 2+2, didynamous, free, petalostamonus, inserted, introrse, the anthers ditheous, connivent, dorsifixed, longitudinal dehiscence; carpels 2, bicarpellary, syncarpous, 4-loculed due to the false septum, basal placentation, one ovule in each locule, gynobasic style present, the stigma bi-fid, disc present. Fruits 4, dry nutlets, oblongoid; seeds small, oblongoid, endospermic.

Uses in references-(The whole plant) Cathartic; Indigestion; As an expectorant; Jaundice; Oedema; Antioxidant activity; Analgesic; Antiinflammatory; Eliminate. (**Leaves**) Biliousness; Polyuria; Pyrexia; Cough; Asthma; Urinary tract infection; Purities; Aspermia. (**Root**) Jaundice. (**Fruit**) Malaria; antipyretic.

Scientific Name : *Cinnamomum tamala* (Buch-Ham.)

Myanmar Name : Karaway

Common Name : Malabar leaf.

Family : Lauraceae

Identification characters :

Trees, bark slightly rough, dark brown. Leaves opposite and decussate, simple, the laminae broadly elliptic, the bases rounded, the margins entire, the tips acute, the lower glabrous, coriaceous. Inflorescences terminal panicle cymes. Flowers bracteates, deciduous, pedicellate, bracteolate, bisexual, complete, irregular, zygomorphic, trimerous, hypogynous; perianth 6-lobed, 2 seriate, synphyllous, the lobes elliptic, cream coloured; stamens 9+3st, 4 whorls of 3 each, adnate to the perianth tube, inserted, introrse, the fourth whorl of 3 staminodes, the anther 4 celled, basifixed, valves dehiscence; carpel-1, monocarpellary, unilocular, pendulous placentation, ovule solitary, the style thick and stout, the stigma discoid. Fruits drupe, ellipsoid; seed 1, ellipsoid, hard, non-endiopermic.

Uses in references- (**Leaf**) Arthritis; Gastrointestinal Colic; Asthma;Cough; Antidote for snake venom and opium intoxication. (**Bark**) Oedema; purities; Gonorrhoea.

Scientific Name : *Michelia champaca* L

Myanmar Name : Sa-ga-war

Common Name : White champaca.

Family : Magnoliaceae

Identification characters :

Trees, branches spreading, dense. Leaves alternate, simple, the laminae ovate-lanceolate, the bases obtuse, the margins entire, the tips acute, petiolate, stipulate, deciduous. Inflorescences axillary and solitary cymes. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, ebracteolate, bisexual, complete, regular, actinomorphic, polymerous, hypogynous; perianth numerous, apophyllous, arranged in three whorls, pale yellow to dark yellow, very fragrant, outer whorl oblong, the whorls linear; stamens numerous, free, spirally arranged, androphore present, the filaments short, anthers dithecous, adnate, inserted, introrse, longitudinal dehiscence; carpels numerous, apocarpous, spirally arranged on the elongated axis, unilocular, parietal placentation, one ovule in each locule, the style short, the stigma truncate, ovary superior. Fruits follicle, winged nut or a berry.

Uses in references- (**Bark**) Dry cough. (**Root or root bark**) Heal boils and Carbuncles. (**Leaf**) Puerperal pyrexia; Eye weakness; Chest pain;Anathematic. (**Flower**) Dysuria; Gastritis;

Promotes kidney function; Natural perfume. **(Fruit and seed)** Inguinal lymph edinitis. **(Stem)** Valuable timber; Furniture making; Construction and cabinetry.

Scientific Name : *Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.)Miers.

Myanmar Name : Sindone-ma-new

Common Name : Guduchi.

Family : Menispermaceae

Identification characters :

Climbing shrub, lianous, stems grooved, glabrous. Leaves alternate, simple, laminae broadly ovate, the bases cordate and large basal lobes, the margins entire, the tips acute, 3-5 costate, the surfaces glabrous, petiolate, exstipulate. Inflorescences axillary and terminal racemes, exceeding leaf length. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, ebracteolate, unisexual, dioecious, trimerous, hypogynous. Male flowers fascicled; sepals 6, aposepalous, 2-seriate, the outer minute, ovate-oblong, the 3 inner one larger, membranous broadly elliptic, concave, petaloid (yellow); petals 6, 2-seriate, equal, broadly spatulate, smaller than sepals; stamens 6, polyandrous, opposite to the petals, the anther 4 celled, adnate, longitudinal dehiscence; pistillode absent. Female flowers solitary; sepals and petals similar to male flowers, staminodes 6, short, carpel 3, apocarpous, on the short fleshy gynophores, each ovary one-carpelled, unilocular, parietal placentation, the ovule solitary, in each locule, the stigma forked, ovary superior. Fruits drupe, reddish; seeds oblongoid.

Uses in references- **(Stem)** Jaundice; Cough; Leprosy; Good for heart;Arthritis; Carminative; Antidote for poisons;Indigestion. **(Leaf)** Jaundice; Diabetes; Rheumatoid arthritis; Antineoplastic; Antioxidant; Hepatoprotective; Hypolipidemic.

Scientific Name : *Myristica fragrans* Houtt.

Myanmar Name : Zadeik-hpo

Common Name : Nutmeg.

Family : Myristicaceae

Identification characters :

Trees. Leaves alternate, simple, the laminae elliptic-lanceolate, the bases obtuse, the margins entire, the tips acuminate, petiolate, exstipulate. Inflorescences axillary fasciculate cymes, dioecious. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate, bracteolate, unisexual, regular, trimerous, hypogynous. Male flowers, perianth synphyllous, 3 lobed, seplid (green), glabrous, deciduous; stamens 9-12, monadelphous, the filaments united to form stamina column, the anthers ditheous, ovoid, sessile, inserted, extrorse, longitudinal dehiscence. Female flowers, perianth similar to the male flower; carpel 1, monocarpellary, unilocular, basal placentation, the style short, the stigma capitate, ovary superior, ovule solitary. Fruits dehiscent drup, globose; seeds enclosed in a fleshy brightly coloured aromatic arid, endosperm copious. **Uses in references-** (Fruit wall) Carminative; Cough; Asthma; Appetizer; Antitode for poisons; Expectorant; Gains weigh. (Fruit) Cholera; Diarrhea; Anaemia; Haemorrhoids; Nausea; Stomach spasms and pain; Intestinal gas.

Scientific Name : *Gardenia coronaria* Buch-Ham.

Myanmar Name : Yingat

Common Name : Encyclopedia of life.

Family : Rubiaceae

Identification characters :

A deciduous trees branches stout, woody, pubescent, buds resinous. Leaves opposite and decussate, simple, the laminae obovate, the bases cuneate, the margins entire, the tips shortly acuminate, petiolate, interpetiolar stipules present, both surfaces glabrous. Inflorescences axillary and terminal 2 to 3 flowered cymes. Flowers large and showy, fragrant, bracteates, subsessile, ebracteolate, bisexual, regular, actinomorphic, pentamerous, epigynous; sepals (5), synsepalous, toothed, tubular, acutely 5 angled, caducous; petals (5), synpetalous, salverform, twisted in bud, the tubes long, the corolla lobe obliquely ovate, petaloid, yellowish-green; stamens 5, polyandrous, alternate to the corolla lobes, petalostamonus, subsessile, attached at the mouth of corolla tube, the anther ditheous, dorsifixed, inserted, introrse, longitudinal dehiscence; carpels (2), bicarpellary, syncarpous, unilocular above, bilocular below, numerous ovules in each locule, parietal placentation, the style long and thick, the stigma 2 lobed, clavate fusiform. Fruits a hard drup, ellipsoid, 5-ribbed, orange to reddish brown when ripe; seeds many, reniform, endospermic.

Uses in references- (Flower) Pyrexia due to either biliary or Chestinfections or Blood dyscrasia. **(Leaf)** Treatment of rhematic pain and bronchitis. **(Fruit)** Cough; Mucotyctic.

Scientific Name : *Alpinia zerumbet* (Pers.) B.L.Burt & R.M.Smith.

Myanmar Name : Padegaw-gyi

Common Name : Shell ginger.

Family : Zingiberaceae

Identification characters :

Perennial shrubs, with under ground aromatic rhizomes. Leaves alternate and distichous, simple, the laminae oblong-lanceolate, the bases cuneate, the margins entire, the tips acuminate, petiole with sheathing, parallel veined, exstipulate. Inflorescences terminal, panicles, densely flowered. Flowers bracteates, pedicellate bracteolate, bisexual, irregular, zygomorphic, trimerous, epigynous; sepals (3), fused, calyx tube funnel-shaped, greenish-white, pubescent outside, persistent; petals (3), fused, corolla tube tubular, greenish-white, shorter than the calyx, the corolla unequal, posterior lobe is larger than others, pubescent outside; stamen 1 fertile, lateral staminodes absent, other staminodes fused to form a labellum, petalostemonous, the filament of fertile stamen grooved, well developed, inserted, introrse, the anthers ditheous, dorsifixed, longitudinal dehiscence; carpels (3), tricarpeal, syncarpous, trilocular, axile placentation, 2-4 ovules in each locule, the style terminal and filiform, within the grooved of fertile filaments, extending between two anther lobes, protruding out as a stigma, the stigma turbinate and ciliate, ovary inferior. Fruits capsules, oblongoid to obovoid, when ripen red, indehiscent.

Uses in references- (Rhizome) Cough; Fever; Heart disease; Asthma; Headache; Colic; Malaria; Expectorant; Blood purifying agent; Carminative. **(Leaf)** Hypotensive; Diuretic; Antiulcer; Alleviate fevers. The leaf and rhizome proven effective agents HIV; Antidiabetic.

Discussion and Conclusion

Fifteen plants are presented in this paper. The plants are arranged in the alphabetical families of scientific names. Only (15) medicinal plants which are under (14) families are mentioned. Out of this Muya-ryi and Hta-La-but are under family Acanthaceae; Aw-za is under Annonaceae; Lin-ne is under Araceae; Ma-ryi is under Caesalpinaceae; Kana-kho is under Euphorbiaceae; Aung-me-nyo is under fabaceae; Gan-gaw is under Calophyllaceae; Pinku-hteik-peik is under Lamiaceae; Karaway is under Lauraceae; Sa-ga-war is under Magnoliaceae; Sindone-ma-new is under Menispermaceae; Zedeik-hpo is under Myristicaceae; Yin-gat is under Rubiaceae; Pedegaw-ryi is under Zingiberaceae.

Bioefficacy of the herbal is provided and the major are therapeutic category to which the herb belongs has been mentioned as follow. Muya-ryi (root), Kana-kho (seed) and Ma-ryi (seed) are used Antidote for scorpion strings. Pinku-hteik-peik (leave) is used in urinary tract-infection. Lin-ne (rhizome), Magyi (bark) and Padegaw-ryi (rhizome) are used anticollic; Sindone-ma-new (stem), Ka-na-kho (seed) and Gan-gaw (anther) are used antileprosy. Hta-la-but (leave) is used for dyeing hairs, shampoo. Zardeik-hpo (fruit) is used Anaemia, Yin-gat (flower) is used blood dyscrasia, Aung-me-nyo is used in antimenstrual disorders and Aw-za, Hta-la-but, Gan-gaw and Padegaw-ryi also used in antidiabetic. This paper should also form the basis for futher work in the important area of traditional medicine and alternative medicine.

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